

PROSPECTS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SCHOOL
EDUCATION IN MULTIMEDIA MEDIA

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Abstract: Taking into account the points presented in this thesis, it can be noted that, in our opinion, the most convenient way to develop media education is the development of educational subjects with the help of information technologies and multimedia technologies.

Key words: media education, media technology, media literacy, mass media, media socialization, media pedagogy.

Introduction:

It can be said that in today's rapidly changing era, the fact that there is a lot of information flow, and being able to distinguish between what is useful and what is necessary for us, is now becoming an important and urgent problem. In such situations, the task of protecting young students from light mass information streams that do not poison their minds has become a duty of all of us. It is very important for all of us to be able to distinguish reliable and unreliable sources in our thinking in order to know whether the information coming in different media and networks is true or false, useful or useless. It is also important to mention that the abundance of information makes the classes interesting and meaningful. It is not an exaggeration to say that it is not an exaggeration to say that it is no longer a problem for a teacher to find information related to the topic in the textbook, or from sources other than the information provided in the textbook. But conveying this much information to the reader (within this time frame) can be a bit of a challenge. The main problem is to sort out the necessary information and deliver it to the reader quickly and easily and, most importantly, in an understandable way. One of the ways to collect information and present it in an easy way is to prepare infographic materials. For example, we can make an infographic slide for a lesson or present it in the form of a poster in the form of a document, or prepare a short video clip. To do this, we need to be familiar with practical programs. Nowadays, lack of computer literacy is like a student who does not know how to read and write. Every teacher needs to have the skills to prepare a presentation, documenting in practical programs on a computer, even at a minimal level. Only after that he can move on to use other opportunities.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In recent years, great positive work has been carried out in higher and secondary special educational institutions in terms of introducing information and communication technologies (ICT), in particular, the use of multimedia technologies to enrich the content of the educational system, to improve the organizational forms and quality.

In our republic, the education system has been fundamentally reformed, and major changes have been made in the system of continuous education, including higher and secondary special education. In particular, in this regard, it is of great importance to achieve the effectiveness of media competence development of students of higher educational institutions of pedagogy.

Among the main trends of world development, the transition to an information society is an important task, that is, the influence of media in all aspects of society is considered an urgent problem. According to the recommendation of the legislative assembly of the European Union Parliamentary Assembly, the production of software tools stimulates the formation of media competence of young people and adults, and is also considered as an integral factor affecting the media culture of modern society [1, 8].

The process of individual-oriented education with the help of multimedia tools requires the development and use of modern, multi-disciplinary, subject-oriented multimedia educational tools. They include a wide database, educational knowledge base, artificial intelligence systems, expert-tutoring systems, laboratory practices with the possibility of creating a mathematical model of the studied process and phenomena.

The concept of multimedia means a set of tools that process information in various forms [2, 36]. Multimedia technologies are a set of tools that process information in various forms. Multimedia technologies primarily include sound and video processing tools. In addition, multiplication (animation) and high-quality graphics are among multimedia technologies. Perhaps, in the future, multimedia tools will allow working with other types of information, for example, virtual reality.

The use of multimedia tools in education provides the following opportunities:

- ensuring the humanization of education;
- increase the efficiency of the educational process;

- development of the student's personal qualities (assimilation, thirst for knowledge, independent education, self-education, ability to improve oneself, creative abilities, applying acquired knowledge in practice ability, interest in learning, attitude to work);
- development of the learner's communicative and social skills;
- with the help of computer tools and information electronic educational resources, the possibilities of individualization and differentiation of open and distance education will be significantly expanded due to the separate (individual) education of each person;
- looking at the learner as an active learning subject, recognizing his value;
- taking into account the personal experience and individual characteristics of the learner;
- conducting independent educational activities, in which the learner studies and develops independently;
- formation of skills in the use of modern educational technologies that help students to adapt to the current rapidly changing social conditions in order to successfully perform their professional tasks [3,4].

Providing interactivity is one of the important achievements of digital multimedia compared to other means of presenting information.

Interactivity refers to the provision of relevant information in accordance with the needs of the learner. Interactivity allows you to control the presentation of information to a certain extent: learners can individually change the settings defined in the program, study the results, respond to the program's request about a specific desire of the user, set the speed of presentation of materials and the number of repetitions.

But it is important to consider a number of aspects when using multimedia. Educational materials presented in multimedia should be easy to understand, provided with modern information and convenient tools.

In order to fully reveal all the possibilities of multimedia technologies and use them effectively, students need the support of a potential (competent) teacher. As with the use of textbooks, in the use of multimedia tools, the educational strategy is enriched with content only when the teacher is engaged not only in providing information, but also in helping, supporting and guiding the learning process.

Presentations enriched with beautiful images or animations are usually more attractive than plain text and can complement the material being presented and provide the necessary emotional level.

Multimedia tools can be used in harmony with different educational directions (styles) and can be used by people with different mental and age characteristics of learning and receiving knowledge: some learners directly and some like to learn and acquire knowledge by hearing and others by watching (video films).

Multimedia tools are effective and promising tools (instruments) of education, which provide the teacher with a large-scale array of information, rather than a traditional source of information; using not only text, graphics, schemes, but also sound, animations, video, etc. In a visual and harmonious way; creates an opportunity to select types of information in a sequence in accordance with the level of reception (perception) and logical learning of learners.

CONCLUSION:

Today, multimedia technologies are one of the promising directions of informatization of the educational process. The introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process is an important condition for the intellectual development of students and pupils and the socio-economic development of our society. For this reason, today's teacher should work tirelessly on himself, possess the necessary qualities for his professional expertise as a person with broad creative thinking, who can effectively use advanced pedagogical and multimedia technologies. The introduction of modern information technologies into the educational process requires the improvement of software and methodological support, the material base, as well as the improvement of the qualifications of teaching specialists. Multimedia tools are also important in improving the qualifications and skills of pedagogues.

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